

Funded by
the European Union

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D1.1 – Comprehensive Project Management Plan, Quality Assurance and Risk Management

Author(s):	Nikolaos Dourvas (CERTH)
Leading Partner:	CERTH
Version - Status:	V1
Submission Date:	30/09/2024
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message: ©iDriving Consortium, 2024-2027. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation, or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Report information

Short Information of the deliverable			
Relevant Work package:	WPI		
Relevant Task:	T1.1. Project management, administration and reporting		
Contributors:	All partners		
Next version Title:	NA	Next version Date:	NA
Official Submission Date:	30/09/2024	Actual Submission Date:	30/09/2024

ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU’s goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

No	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS	CERTH	EL
2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL
3	AUSTRIATECH - GESELLSCHAFT DES BUNDES FUR AT TECHNOLOGIEPOLITISCHE MASSNAHMEN GMBH	AUSTRIATECH	AT
4	UNIVERSITE GUSTAVE EIFFEL	UNI.EIFFEL	FR
5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
6	INGARTEK CONSULTING SL	ING	ES
7	INFRA PLAN KONZALTNIG JDOO ZA USLUGE	INFRA PLAN	HR
8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
9	NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	LU
10	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	SIMAVI	RO
11	ALP.Lab GmbH	ALP.LAB	AT
12	MUNICIPALITY OF ALBA IULIA	AIM	RO

13	DRAXIS RESEARCH VENTURES ASTIKI MI EL KERDOSKOPIKI ETAIRIA	DREVEN	EL
14	PRAVO I INTERNET FOUNDATION	LIF	BG
15	DIMOS THESSALONIKIS	THESSALONIKI	EL
16	GRAD KARLOVAC	COK	HR
17	MOBILYSIS SARL	MOBILYSIS SARL	CH

Version History

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Description
0.1	23/09/2024	Nikolaos Dourvas	CERTH	Draft provided to internal reviewers
0.2	25/09/2024	Charalampos Chatzimallis, Martha Papadopoulou, Pantelis Velanas	ACCELI	Internal review provided and comments addressed from CERTH
0.3	27/09/2024	Zoi Dimitriadou	DREVEN	Internal review provided and comments addressed from CERTH
0.4	27/09/2024	Rada Stoilova	LIF	Internal review provided and comments addressed from CERTH
1.0	30/09/2024	Nikolaos Dourvas	CERTH	Submission to EC

Table of Contents

ABOUT iDRIVING -----	2
1 Introduction -----	9
2 Organizational Structure and quality assurance responsibilities ---	10
2.1 Individual responsibilities and competencies -----	10
2.1.1 Project Coordinator -----	10
2.1.2 Scientific Manager -----	11
2.1.3 Technical Manager -----	11
2.1.4 Data Protection Advisor -----	12
2.1.5 Dissemination Manager -----	12
2.1.6 Work Package Leaders (WP Leaders) -----	12
2.2 Group responsibilities and competencies -----	13
2.2.1 Management Office -----	13
2.2.2 Executive Board (EB) -----	13
2.2.3 External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) -----	15
2.2.4 Quality Evaluation Group (QEG) -----	15
3 Communication and Reporting Guidelines -----	16
3.1 Communication procedures -----	16
3.1.1 General Communication between partners of the Consortium -----	16
3.1.2 Meetings -----	16
3.1.3 Mailing Lists -----	17
3.2 Information Management -----	17
3.2.1 Collaboration tools -----	17
3.2.2 Document Templates -----	18
3.2.3 File Naming and Numbering -----	18
3.2.4 Actions, meeting minutes, and open issues logging -----	18
3.2.5 Reporting guidelines -----	19
3.2.6 Six-month Internal Reports -----	19
3.2.7 Deliverables submission protocol -----	19
3.2.8 Periodic Reports -----	20
3.2.9 Final Report -----	21
4 Ensuring high-quality research & development -----	22
4.1 Ensuring High Quality Research -----	22
4.2 Ensuring high-quality SW development -----	22
4.3 Ethics -----	24
5 Risk Management and Strategies for Mitigating Quality Issues ---	25
5.1 Risk Management -----	25
5.2 Corrective Action Procedure -----	26

5.2.1	Procedure	26
5.2.2	Non-Conformity Report	27
6	Scientific/Technical/User Objectives (SO/TO/UO) and Performance Indicators (KPI)	28
6.1	SO.1 - KPIs 1-3	28
6.2	SO.2 - KPIs 4-7	28
6.3	SO.3 - KPIs 8-11	29
6.4	SO.4 - KPIs 12-13	30
6.5	TO.1 & KPIs 15-18	31
6.6	UO.1 & KPIs	31
6.7	UO.2 & KPIs	32
7	Summary	33
A.	APPENDIX	34
A.1	Logos	34
	Quality of information – Disclaimer	34
	iDriving Logo	34
A.2	Presentation and Document Templates	35
	A.2.1 Presentation Template	35
	A.2.2. Deliverable Template Front Page	36
	A.2.3 Deliverable Internal review form	36
	A.2.4 Minutes Template	37
	PROJECT FACTS	38

Table of tables

Table 1 - iDriving Work Packages	12
Table 2 - Meetings already conducted/planned	17
Table 3 - Risk Matrix	26
Table 4 - SO.1 Indicators	28
Table 5 - SO.2 Indicators	29
Table 6 - SO.3 Indicators	29
Table 7 - SO.4 Indicators	30
Table 8 - TO.1 Indicators	31
Table 9 - UO.1 Indicators	31
Table 10 - UO.2 Indicators	32

Table of figures

Figure 1 - Risk identification process	25
--	----

Figure 2 - EU Flag & Funding Statement	34
Figure 3 - Project Logo	35
Figure 4 - Project Presentation Template	35
Figure 5 - Deliverable reports 1st page	36
Figure 6 - Deliverables' internal review form	36
Figure 7 - Minutes Template	37

Glossary

WP(s)	Work Package(s)
DoA	Description of Action
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
PC	Project Coordinator
SM	Scientific Manager
TM	Technical Manager
ST	Support Team
DPA	Data Protection Advisor
DM	Dissemination Manager
MO	Management Office
EB	Executive Board
EEAB	External Expert Advisory Board
QEH	Quality Evaluation Group
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable, and Reusable
DMP	Data Management Plan
ToC	Table of Contents
GA	Grant Agreement

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

CA	Consortium Agreement
CFS	Certificates of Financial Statements
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicles
KPI	Key Performance Indicator

Executive summary

This document represents the first deliverable of iDriving's Work Package 1 (WP1), focusing on Project Coordination, Management, and Risk Analysis. It offers a detailed overview of the project's overall management framework, covering aspects such as quality assurance, risk management, and data management. These tools are essential for promoting effective communication within the consortium, which is key to reaching the project's milestones.

The iDriving Project Management and Quality Assurance Handbook serves as a supplementary guide to the information outlined in the Grant Agreement's Description of Action (DoA). It covers key areas including project planning, scheduling, consortium organization, management procedures, risk assessment, and quality assurance. This plan will be updated as needed throughout the project lifecycle, with any changes reflected in the progress reporting deliverables.

This document clarifies the roles of consortium partners, outlines the project's objectives, defines decision-making bodies and processes, and introduces the tools used in the daily management and coordination of project activities. Additionally, the risk management plan has been thoroughly reviewed and updated from its proposal-stage version.

The deliverable is organized into the following sections:

1. Introduction
2. Organizational Structure and Quality Assurance Responsibilities.
3. Communication and Reporting Guidelines.
4. Ensuring high-quality research.
5. Risk Management and Measures for addressing quality flaws.
6. Project Objectives and Performance Indicators (KPIs).
7. An Annex at the end of this document including the project's templates for: deliverables and their review, meetings' agenda, minutes, presentations, etc.

1 Introduction

An effective management strategy for iDriving is essential to ensure smooth collaboration within the Consortium and to achieve the project's ultimate goals. This report provides a detailed analysis of the project's organizational structure, outlining roles at both the group and individual levels, as well as the protocols for communication within the consortium and with the European Commission. Additionally, this report serves as a reference for organizing consortium meetings, as well as the production, review, and submission of deliverables.

Furthermore, as part of this report, a comprehensive Quality Assurance Plan (QAP) is developed to guide the consortium throughout the project. The QAP establishes quality standards and outline the necessary processes to ensure alignment with the project's objectives. Specifically, the QAP:

- Defines the criteria and benchmarks for evaluating process quality.
- Introduces strategies to meet the proposed quality standards.
- Implements compliance measures to ensure adherence to quality guidelines.
- Proposes methodologies for identifying potential deviations and addressing them.

To ensure the effective implementation of the QAP, the following steps are taken:

- Clearly presenting and acknowledging the consortium's organizational structure, making it known to all members.
- Assigning clear responsibilities related to quality assurance among the partners.
- Sharing timely guidelines for effective communication, coordination, and reporting within the consortium, particularly regarding the production, review, and submission of deliverables.
- Providing a toolkit to ensure high-quality research and development operations throughout the project.
- Proposing a strategy for identifying risks or deviations (scientific, technical, administrative, or other) and recommend solutions for addressing these issues.
- Regularly updating the list of research and performance indicators for each activity.

2 Organizational Structure and quality assurance responsibilities

The organizational structure of the iDriving Consortium has been carefully designed to ensure:

1. Timely and effective decision-making.
2. Active participation of all partners in the decision-making processes.
3. Management mechanisms that ensure the achievement of iDriving's objectives within the specified timeline, while maintaining high-quality results and adhering to the budget.
4. Smooth cooperation with competent authorities and the European Commission.
5. Engagement of key experts, providing their specialization and expertise when needed.
6. Effective methods to prevent or resolve disputes.

The structure consists of the following boards, teams, and individual roles:

- Management Team, which includes three key roles:
 - ✚ Project Coordinator (PC)
 - ✚ Scientific Manager (SM)
 - ✚ Technical Manager (TM)
- Support Team (ST), composed of:
 - ✚ Data Protection Advisor (DPA)
 - ✚ Dissemination Manager (DM)
 - ✚ Management Office (MO)
- Executive Board (EB), comprising:
 - ✚ The Coordinator
 - ✚ One representative from each Consortium partner
- External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)
- Quality Evaluation Group (QEG)

2.1 Individual responsibilities and competencies

This section outlines the key responsibilities and obligations of each of the previously mentioned teams, boards, and roles.

2.1.1 Project Coordinator

Dr. Stefanos Vrochidis (CERTH) will act as the Project Coordinator (PC) and Technical Manager (TM) for iDriving. In this role, his duties will encompass:

- Facilitating effective and ongoing communication within the Consortium.
- Acting as the primary liaison with the European Commission (EC), ensuring proper representation of the Consortium.

- Managing and supporting the execution of all plans, tasks, and activities assigned to partners.
- Coordinating the smooth execution of the project and ensuring the achievement of its objectives.
- Monitoring project progress to maintain quality and ensure correct implementation of actions.
- Safeguarding the Consortium's rights and ensuring partners fulfil their obligations.
- Resolving conflicts through established corrective mechanisms. The Consortium Agreement specifies the procedure for the resolution of conflicts. Potential conflicts will be identified by the Partners and brought to the attention of the Project Coordinator. The PC will first try to resolve this through discussion or by calling a meeting, hopefully towards a unanimous decision. If that fails, the PC will seek a decision by vote within the GA. As a last resort, the conflict may be referred to the procedure for the settlement of disputes that is specified in the CA.
- Executing all responsibilities outlined in the Grant Agreement, including ensuring timely payments.
- Presiding over the General Assembly (GA) during its meetings.

2.1.2 Scientific Manager

Prof. Ioannis Papamichail (TUC) will act as the Scientific Manager for the iDriving project. In this role, he will:

- Supervise and monitor all research activities to ensure alignment with the project's objectives.
- Provide scientific expertise and guidance to the Project Coordinator.
- Ensure progress and high-quality outcomes in the research initiatives and their associated outputs.

2.1.3 Technical Manager

Dr. Konstantinos Ioanndis and Dr. Nikolaos Dourvas (CERTH) will both take on the roles of Deputy Technical Manager (TM) and Deputy Coordinator for iDriving. In this capacity, they will:

- Ensure the project's technological goals are met and facilitate smooth technical progress.
- Advise the Project Coordinator on technical issues.
- Support Work Package (WP) leaders in achieving the objectives of each WP.
- Identify and manage technical risks and objectives in coordination with the Project Coordinator and WP Leaders.
- Oversee the technical quality of deliverables.
- Promote collaboration and planning among consortium members, ensuring effective information flow.

- Lead and participate in WPs leader meetings and technical meetings for the relevant scientific and/or technical WPs.

2.1.4 Data Protection Advisor

Ms Rada Stoilova (LIF) will take on the role of Data Protection Advisor. In this capacity, she will:

- Ensure that all datasets created and processed follow the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for data management.
- Oversee the development and regular updating of a comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP) early in the project, which will guide data management throughout the project's duration.
- Coordinate the creation of an Intellectual Property Rights Plan that details the management, sharing, and protection of intellectual property within the project.

2.1.5 Dissemination Manager

Mr. Charalampos Chatzimallis (ACCELIGENCE) will act as a Dissemination Manager for the iDriving project. In this capacity, he will:

- Organize and coordinate regular teleconferences for the dissemination activities within Work Package 7 (WP7)
- Evaluate the project's progress in achieving its dissemination objectives.
- Monitor all dissemination activities throughout the project's duration.
- Advise the Project Coordinator on dissemination-related issues.

2.1.6 Work Package Leaders (WP Leaders)

To ensure streamlined and effective coordination, iDriving is organized into seven work packages (WPs), each with specific objectives and timelines. Each WP is led by a Consortium partner, who is responsible for the following tasks:

- Planning the work within the WP and assigning tasks to participating partners.
- Ensuring that both the project and individual WP timelines are adhered to.
- Identifying deviations and implementing corrective actions as needed.
- Preparing and submitting necessary reports to the Project Coordinator.
- Ensuring the quality, accuracy, and timely completion of the WP's objectives, deliverables, and milestones.

A WP leaders meeting, chaired by the Technical Manager/ Deputy Coordinator, is held at least once a month to ensure proper coordination and communication between Work Packages. The seven WPs of iDriving, along with their titles and leading organizations are presented in the following table:

Table 1 - iDriving Work Packages

WP	Title	Leader
WP1	Project Coordination & Management	CERTH

WP2	Enhanced criteria catalogue, Use cases and Requirements definition	INFRA PLAN
WP3	Advanced V2I Data Management and On-site Applications for Enhanced Safety	TEKNIKER
WP4	Intelligent Edge Computing and Monitoring for Safer and Well-maintained Roads	CERTH
WP5	Dynamic Learning and Digital Twins for Safety Control and Maintenance	UNI EIFFEL
WP6	Trial Implementation, User Training and Evaluation Procedures	AUSTRIATECH
WP7	Impact creation & exploitation	ACCELIGENCE

2.2 Group responsibilities and competencies

2.2.1 Management Office

The Management Office (MO), led by the Project Coordinator (PC) from CERTH, handles daily administrative tasks and plays a crucial role in coordinating research activities within the Consortium. Its key responsibilities include:

- Facilitate effective communication on administrative matters between the European Commission (EC) authorities and the Consortium, while also enhancing internal communication among beneficiaries.
- Manage the distribution of funds to partners according to the allocation plan and ensure their proper use.
- Oversee and coordinate the timely preparation and submission of deliverables, reports, and statements.
- Handle contract-related issues within the Consortium, including amendments and dispute resolutions.
- Support, coordinate, and facilitate meetings throughout the project's duration.
- Assist partners, WP leaders, and the management team with both strategic and operational aspects.

2.2.2 Executive Board (EB)

The Executive Board (EB) is the formal and highest decision-making body of the iDriving Consortium. Chaired by the Project Coordinator (PC) and supported by the Scientific Manager (SM), Technical Manager (TM), and one representative from each partner, the EB is responsible for overseeing the internal coordination of project activities among beneficiaries. Each EB representative is empowered to deliberate, negotiate, and make decisions on all relevant matters.

Associated Partners are excluded from voting on and vetoing certain decisions of the Executive Board (as specified in Section 6.3.7 in CA), and their votes are not counted towards the quorum for the following matters:

- Modifications to the financial aspects of the Consortium Plan
- Allocation of the EU contribution among the Beneficiaries
- Proposals to amend Annex 2 of the Grant Agreement, subject to approval by the Granting Authority
- Decisions pertaining to Section 7.1.4 of the Consortium Agreement (CA)

The chairperson shall convene ordinary meetings of the Executive Board at least once every 6 (six) months and shall also convene extraordinary meetings at any time upon written request of any Member. Meetings of the Executive Board may also be held by tele- or videoconference or other telecommunication means provided that the chairperson of the Executive Board is able to identify all attendees.

Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if:

1. The Project Coordinator circulates to all Members of the Executive Board a suggested decision with a deadline for responses of at least ten (10) calendar days after receipt by a Party and
2. The decision is agreed by fifty-one percent (51 %) of all Parties.

The Project Coordinator shall inform all the Members of the outcome of the vote.

A veto, according to Section 6.3.5 in CA, may be submitted up to ten (10) calendar days after receipt of this information.

The decision will be binding after the Project Coordinator sends a notification to all Members. The Project Coordinator will keep records of the votes and make them available to the Parties on request.

The following decisions shall be taken by the Executive Board:

1. Content, finances, and intellectual property rights
 - Proposals for changes to Annexes 1 and 2 of the Grant Agreement to be agreed by the Granting Authority
 - Changes to the Consortium Plan
 - Modifications or withdrawal of Background in Attachment 1 (Background Included)
 - Additions to Attachment 3 (List of Third Parties for simplified transfer according to Section 8.3.2 in CA)
 - Additions to Attachment 4 (Identified entities under the same control)
2. Evolution of the consortium
 - Entry of a new Party to the Project and approval of the settlement on the conditions of the accession of such a new Party
 - Withdrawal of a Party from the Project and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal
 - Proposal to the Granting Authority for a change of the Coordinator
 - Proposal to the Granting Authority for suspension of all or part of the Project

- Proposal to the Granting Authority for termination of the Project and the Consortium Agreement
- 3. Breach, defaulting party status and litigation
 - Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under the Consortium Agreement (CA) or the Grant Agreement (GA)
 - Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
 - Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party
 - Termination of a Defaulting Party's participation in the consortium and measures relating thereto
 - Steps to be taken for litigation purposes and the coverage of litigation costs in case of joint claims of the parties of the consortium against a Party (Section 4.3, Section 7.1.4 in CA)
- 4. Appointments
 - On the basis of the Grant Agreement, the appointment, if necessary, of:
 - ✚ External Advisory Board Members

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the Executive Board, members shall rearrange the tasks of the Parties concerned. Such a rearrangement shall take into consideration any prior legitimate commitments which cannot be canceled.

2.2.3 External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB)

An External Expert Advisory Board (EEAB) may be appointed if needed. In this case, it will be steered by the Executive Board. The EEAB shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the Executive board. The Project Coordinator will ensure that each member of the EEAB signs a Declaration of Confidentiality. The Project Coordinator will also record the minutes of the EEAB meetings and submit them to the Executive Board. EEAB members may attend Executive Board meetings by invitation but will not have voting rights.

The decision on whether to appoint an External Expert Advisory Board will be discussed at the 1st Plenary Meeting of iDriving, scheduled for the first quarter of 2025.

2.2.4 Quality Evaluation Group (QEG)

The Quality Evaluation Group (QEG) is responsible for ensuring that partners comply with quality standards and for facilitating reporting on the achievement of the project's objectives. The QEG consists of the Management Office (MO) and internal reviewers, who are tasked with evaluating all deliverables.

3 Communication and Reporting Guidelines

3.1 Communication procedures

3.1.1 General Communication between partners of the Consortium

CERTH will manage communication within the Consortium through various channels, including emails, calls, and online voice/chat programs. Scanned documents should be sent via email, while administrative documents should be transferred using conventional postal services. Day-to-day communications will primarily occur via email. To facilitate this, several mailing lists have been established: a general list, one for the Executive Board, one for administrative matters, and several dedicated to specific Work Packages (3.1.3).

To reduce email traffic and ensure easy access to project documents, CERTH will maintain a secure Microsoft SharePoint repository. Instead of sending documents via email, the responsible partner will upload relevant materials to SharePoint and notify the other partners, allowing them to easily locate and access the files. All evolving documents, including multiple versions created by various partners, will be stored in the shared repository to prevent confusion and errors.

3.1.2 Meetings

In line with the CA, notifications and agendas for project meetings must be shared at least 14 calendar days in advance, allowing participants time to review and submit written suggestions for additional agenda items. The PC or the Deputy Coordinators will preside over consortium meetings, while each WP Leader will chair the respective WP meetings.

Working documents should be uploaded to the project's repository no later than 5 working days before the meeting. Draft minutes, prepared by the organizing partner, will be circulated to participants within 10 calendar days after the meeting. Any suggested revisions will be reviewed, and the final agreed minutes will be uploaded to the repository. If no objections are raised within 5 days, the minutes will be considered approved.

To date, the physical Kick-off meeting for iDriving was successfully held as planned during M1 on July 16th-17th 2024 in Thessaloniki. The project aims to organize two physical/plenary meetings annually, with the exact timing and location to be tentatively determined within the first 6 months of the project (see Table 2).

In the interim, each WP leader will conduct monthly teleconference meetings (this can be changed, depending on the decision of the WP contributors and the Project Management Team) to coordinate and track the progress of their respective WP.

Table 2 - Meetings already conducted/planned

Type of meeting	Participants	Venue	Date	Project Month
Kick Off Meeting	Consortium Partners	Thessaloniki	16-17 July 2024	M01
Plenary Meeting	Consortium Partners	To be defined	1 st quarter 2025	M07-M08

3.1.3 Mailing Lists

A total of 10 mailing lists have been created, with each of the 7 WPs having its own list that includes the contact details of the involved beneficiaries. In addition, there is a general list ('ALL') and an 'admin' list for administrative matters. The 'GA' list contains the email addresses of the authorized representatives of the beneficiaries for voting purposes. Email subscriptions for all mailing lists are available through the project's repository, with CERTH responsible for their management and administration. To prevent spam, only list members are permitted to send emails to the respective lists. The partners should inform CERTH via email to update (add/remove) the participants in this list.

3.2 Information Management

3.2.1 Collaboration tools

A dedicated repository has already been established to manage iDriving's operations and enhance partner collaboration. This platform facilitates file sharing, document uploads, and real-time editing, allowing multiple users to access and modify content simultaneously.

The repository stands as a central hub for project-related information, including contact details, management structures, meeting schedules, and WP-specific content.

Beyond its administrative role, the repository will support project tasks with dedicated pages for each WP, outlining tasks, deliverables' submission time plan, and resource allocation. It also features sections for future planning, action items, and open issues, providing a comprehensive overview of pending tasks and key considerations.

Consortium members can add, edit, or comment on existing content within the repository, as well as upload various file types such as Excel sheets, images, or templates for confidential deliverables and presentations, ensuring consistency and uniformity across the project.

The repository serves as the central hub for storing meeting minutes, approved presentations, and dissemination or publication activities. CERTH manages the repository, and each partner designates representatives to access and utilize it.

For coordinating online meetings throughout the project, the GoToMeeting and MICROSOFT TEAMS platforms will be used. CERTH, as coordinator, along with WP Leaders, will schedule meetings as necessary, providing partners with access links and selecting the most suitable platform for communication.

3.2.2 Document Templates

To maintain consistency in the project's presentations and internal documents, and to ensure that all necessary information is included in each deliverable, ACCELI will create and distribute dedicated templates through the repository. The following templates will be made available:

- A template for the deliverables in MS Word, along with the deliverable internal review form
- A template for meeting minutes in MS Word
- A template for meeting presentations in MS PowerPoint
- A template for the internal technical and financial review

3.2.3 File Naming and Numbering

Deliverables Naming:

<iDriving_WPX_DX.Y_vZ.W>

Example: "iDriving_WP1_D1.1_v0.1.docx"

Presentations' Naming:

<iDriving_Nameofmeeting_WPX_vZ.W">

Example: "iDriving_KOM_WP1_v1.0.pptx"

Deliverable Internal review forms' naming:

<iDriving_Reviewform_DX.Y_Vz.w.>

Example: "iDriving_Reviewform_D1.1_v0.1.docx"

To manage large file attachments and reduce email traffic, all documents will be uploaded to the repository. Once uploaded, the relevant partners will receive an email notification containing a link to access the document.

3.2.4 Actions, meeting minutes, and open issues logging

Maintaining logs and monitoring unresolved issues are essential tasks that require ongoing attention. To support this, a specific section is allocated for recording action items and deadlines across all work packages. Regular and timely updates from WP Leaders are vital to ensure that tasks are completed within the specified time frame. After each meeting, minutes are documented and, with the necessary approval, uploaded to the repository under the corresponding meeting page. A template for meeting minutes is provided in the Appendix (A.2.4 Minutes Template).

3.2.5 Reporting guidelines

To track the project's progress and ensure adherence to contractual requirements, various reports will be produced throughout the course of iDriving. These reports will include:

- internal reports (with a technical and a financial aspect) on a six-month basis,
- deliverables,
- periodic, mid-term report with cost statements included (M18),
- a final report.

3.2.6 Six-month Internal Reports

As project coordinator, CERTH will request biannual reports from each partner to ensure effective monitoring of planned efforts. To simplify the process, CERTH will provide report templates and send email reminders at the end of each six-month period approximately. Partners are expected to submit their reports within one month following the end of the reporting period. These reports will include, among other details:

- A summary of technical activities and progress made,
- Issues encountered and corresponding corrective actions,
- A list of deliverables due during that period, and
- The completion status of each WP/TASK, expressed as a percentage based on the work completed.

CERTH will then consolidate the reports submitted by the partners into a comprehensive project report, which will serve as input for subsequent periodic reports.

3.2.7 Deliverables submission protocol

As part of its duties, the coordinator is responsible for submitting all deliverables to the Commission via the appropriate channels, ensuring compliance with security regulations, even for deliverables it does not directly prepare. CERTH will collect electronic copies of the deliverables from the responsible partners for review and verification at least ten working days before the submission deadline.

The process for approving and ensuring the quality of deliverables will proceed as follows:

- **60 days before submission:** The Deliverable Leader sends a draft Table of Contents (ToC) to the WP Leader. (Review deadline: 5 days; deadline to address review comments: 5 days).
- **50-30 days before submission:** The Deliverable Leader, along with contributing partners, prepares the first draft of the deliverable.
- **30 days before submission:** The Deliverable Leader sends the first draft of the deliverable to the WP Leader. (Review deadline: 5 days; deadline to address review comments: 5 days).

- **20 days before submission:** The deliverable is sent to internal reviewers. (Review deadline: 5 days; deadline to address review comments: 5 days).
- **10 days before submission:** All comments are addressed, and the final version is submitted to the Coordination Team for a final quality review, after which the Coordinator submits the deliverable.

Deliverables that span multiple work areas may involve different internal reviewers assigned to each relevant section. Once the review process is complete, the Project Coordinator is responsible for submitting the final deliverable to the Commission.

3.2.8 Periodic Reports

The Consortium is required to submit periodic reports to the Commission within 60 days after the conclusion of each 18-month period (M18, M36), in line with the guidelines specified in the Grant Agreement. These reports, based on a template provided by the European Commission, will include:

- A summary of iDriving's progress toward its objectives, including the completion of milestones and deliverables.
- A status update on the work packages (WPs) and tasks, reflecting their percentage of completion based on activities undertaken.

The financial section of the periodic report will contain:

- Individual and consolidated financial statements for all beneficiaries and affiliated entities.
- An explanation of resource usage, or a detailed cost reporting table if required.
- Certificates on the Financial Statements (CFS), if applicable.

The financial statements must outline the eligible costs and contributions for each budget category, and for the final payment, the revenues generated for the action. All eligible costs and contributions should be declared, even if they exceed the amounts stated in the estimated budget. Any amounts not declared in the individual financial statements will not be considered by the granting authority.

By signing the financial statements directly in the Portal Periodic Reporting tool, the beneficiaries confirm that:

- The information provided is complete, accurate, and truthful.
- The declared costs and contributions are eligible (as per Article 6 of the GA).
- The declared costs and contributions are supported by adequate records and documentation (as per Article 20) that can be provided upon request (as per Article 19) or during checks, reviews, audits, and investigations (as per Article 25).
- For the final periodic report, all relevant revenues have been declared (if required; as per Article 22 of the GA).

Beneficiaries are also required to submit the financial statements of any affiliated entities (if applicable). In the event of recoveries (as per Article 22 of the GA), beneficiaries will be held accountable for the financial statements of their affiliated entities.

3.2.9 Final Report

The final report must be prepared and submitted to the European Commission within the designated timeframes. This report, along with all relevant documentation, such as reports and deliverables, will be archived by the European Commission. The final report must include:

- A comprehensive summary of the project's outcomes and conclusions.
- A dedicated section detailing the project's broader societal impact, addressing ethical considerations and the strategy for utilizing the project's foreground.
- A summary of the efforts made, the actual work carried out, and the results achieved in accordance with the Grant Agreement.
- An explanation of which objectives were met, including an assessment of the applicability of the outcomes to other fields or activities.
- A non-publishable section containing technical details, research findings, evaluations, and recommendations for future research, development, and potential applications.

4 Ensuring high-quality research & development

Maintaining high standards in both research and development is essential for meeting the project's objectives. Therefore, this section is divided into two parts. The first part details the framework used to ensure the quality of the research, while the second part focuses on the procedures designed to maintain high standards throughout the development process.

4.1 Ensuring High Quality Research

The iDriving consortium is a multidisciplinary team with expertise in road safety and traffic management, carefully selected to meet the diverse needs of the project. To ensure high-quality research, the consortium will focus on the following:

- Reviewing the current landscape of road safety and driving efficiency technologies and initiatives, establishing a foundation for the project's outcomes.
- Assessing the target audiences and their specific needs, thereby enhancing support for the project's results and highlighting their potential to improve efficiency, safety, and sustainable road transport.
- Incorporating insights and findings from other relevant multidisciplinary research efforts and industrial products.
- Sharing project work at scientific conferences and venues.
- Producing high-quality deliverables.
- Monitoring the progress of objectives using predefined performance indicators.
- Utilizing self-assessment tools to develop quality software.

In terms of publications, iDriving Consortium partners will actively pursue opportunities to publish and present their work in reputable scientific journals and conferences. The consortium aims to achieve at least 25 scientific publications, including journal articles and conference papers. To maintain consistent quality in iDriving's deliverable reports, the process outlined in Section 3.2.7 will be strictly followed.

4.2 Ensuring high-quality SW development

The iDriving consortium is an interdisciplinary team with expertise in road safety and traffic management. Members were carefully chosen to address the project's diverse requirements. The consortium places a strong emphasis on international collaboration to deliver comprehensive and interoperable solutions.

iDriving aims to improve road safety through the integration of V2I systems, advanced hardware, and innovative software, including predictive safety models and real-time alerts. The project is designed to address both urban and rural challenges by focusing on incident prediction, maintenance optimization, and efficient monitoring. End-users and municipalities will be involved throughout all phases, utilizing a framework similar to the ADDIE model.

The project will undergo three development and evaluation cycles. In the first cycle (M01-M09), user needs for both urban and rural applications will be identified, leading to the development of an initial iDriving architecture by M12 and a prototype evaluation by M22. Insights from this phase will guide the second cycle, resulting in an updated prototype by M26 and an additional evaluation phase extending through M30. The final prototype and evaluation phase will conclude the project by M36.

The development process in iDriving, following the outlined Development Lifecycle, involves the following steps:

- Analysis
- Design
- Development
- Implementation
- Evaluation

Key roles during the development phase include the Technical Manager, who oversees technical advancements, monitors technical KPIs and ensures the integration of solutions; the WP Leader, who is responsible for managing a WP, ensuring adherence to WP indicators, and representing the WP team; and the Team, consisting of the partners contributing to each WP.

During the development process, the following steps are undertaken:

Planning: Requirements for high-level work are outlined during planning meetings. The Technical Manager clarifies which components should be delivered within the set timeframe.

Execution: The Technical Manager is updated on the progress made during relevant meetings, where the team reports on challenges faced and tasks completed.

Monitoring and Control: Regular brief meetings assess progress against goals and determine necessary adaptations for any iterations. The Technical Manager and WP Leader may hold individual meetings to adjust task management and prioritize activities, with new tasks added to the list if necessary.

To ensure software quality, the following tools and techniques will be applied:

Continuous Integration: Developers will frequently integrate their work, allowing for early detection of issues and seamless coordination with other application

components. Automation tools will support this process, running validation tests to detect flaws, reduce errors, and accelerate development and integration. This approach helps assess project quality based on predefined indicators and minimizes regression errors during development.

Coding Standards and Guidelines: Adhering to established metrics and quality standards will ensure best practices in software development, helping the final product meet the project's requirements.

Version Control: A robust version control system will maintain a complete, auditable history of all changes made to the source code, enabling the team to revert to any previous state when needed. To ensure rigorous application of the chosen methodology throughout the development cycles, appropriate tools will be selected and used. Different tool packages are being evaluated to support platform monitoring, management, and requirement tracking.

4.3 Ethics

Ethics-related procedures to be followed by all partners throughout the project duration, covering data security, ethics/privacy compliance, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) protection, and overall project safety, will be outlined in future deliverables. A detailed description will be available in the "Data Governance and Intellectual Property Rights Handbook" (Deliverable D1.2), which will be updated periodically as specified in the Grant Agreement. Any ethical concerns that arise during the project will be addressed and documented in periodic project reports. Publicly accessible findings related to ethics and social impact will be included in relevant deliverables.

5 Risk Management and Strategies for Mitigating Quality Issues

During the project's duration, risks and other problematic conditions may emerge from internal or external sources. The goal of risk management is to proactively identify, mitigate, and minimize potential threats through early detection and appropriate action. A Risk Contingency Plan will be developed for T1.3 covering the entire project timeline.

5.1 Risk Management

Each WP will maintain a dedicated WP Risk Log, where stakeholders will track potential risks related to their work package. These risks will be reported to the Coordinator and Technical Manager for identification and mitigation and shared with other WP leaders. If challenges that impact multiple WPs arise, the leaders will collaborate to address them together.

The overall risk management strategy will follow the European Commission's guidelines for risk assessment and mitigation. Risks will initially be identified using a self-assessment approach. This process may be initiated either by the Project Coordinator, who will inform the consortium during a project meeting (top-down approach), or by individual project members who notify the WP Leader, who will then communicate the information to the Coordinator (bottom-up approach). The step-by-step process for identifying and managing risks is depicted in the figure below:

Figure 1 - Risk identification process

Risks will be evaluated using two key criteria: the likelihood of the risk occurring and its potential impact. Both factors will be measured on a scale from one (1) to three (3), with higher values indicating a greater probability or more significant impact. The following matrix demonstrates this risk assessment method.

Table 3 - Risk Matrix

Likelihood/Impact	Low	Medium	High
Low	0	1	2
Medium	1	1	2
High	2	2	3

The risk matrix will be employed throughout iDriving's lifecycle as a tool for identifying and evaluating risks, helping to determine the most suitable risk mitigation strategies.

The WP Risk Log will include detailed records of the various risk elements, such as the person or group responsible for monitoring and assessing the risk (e.g., the WP leader in a bottom-up approach or the Project Coordinator in a top-down approach), a short description of the risk, its current status (whether resolved or ongoing), the activities or milestones affected, the probability of the risk materializing according to the matrix, and its potential impact. The impact will be classified as low, medium, or high, depending on how long the resolution might take (up to 1 PM, up to 3 PM, or the possibility of compromising the project outcomes if left unresolved). The log will also include the mitigation strategy, outlining the steps to either lower the likelihood of the risk occurring or reduce its impact should it happen.

5.2 Corrective Action Procedure

This section outlines the corrective actions to be taken in the event of non-compliance. The objective is to define the process applicable to all outputs generated within the iDriving project, including documents and software. The specific procedure is detailed below.

5.2.1 Procedure

This procedure outlines the approach for managing non-conformity issues within the iDriving project. It begins with the identification of non-compliance and details each step through to the implementation of corrective actions, pending approval.

- The process starts with the identification of the non-conformity by either the Internal Reviewer or the Project Coordinator (PC). Once identified, the FACTSHEET and NON-CONFORMITY sections of the relevant report are completed accordingly.
- The report is then shared with the WP leader of the affected WP to assess whether the issue is limited to their WP or affects others as well. If it only

impacts their WP, the WP leader proposes corrective measures. If multiple WPs are involved, the PC assumes responsibility for this step.

- The relevant stakeholder (either the WP leader or the PC) will propose corrective actions to address the issue.
- The Executive Board will then decide whether to approve and implement the recommended actions.

5.2.2 Non-Conformity Report

Upon completion of the corrective action process, a detailed report will be created to document the key aspects of the identified issue, the corrective measures taken, and the resolution of the issue. This report will follow a predefined structure, comprising four main sections: (i) Factsheet, (ii) Non-Conformity, (iii) Suggested Corrective Action, and (iv) Resolution.

In the first section, the report should include the following details: (i) document type (report), (ii) document status (final or draft), (iii) reference number, (iv) file name, (v) security classification, (vi) reviewer information, and (vii) the date the issue was detected.

The second section should provide a more in-depth description of the non-conformity, including: (i) the activity during which the non-conformity was identified (such as a review or software testing), (ii) the reference for the related activity, and (iii) a clear description of the non-conformity.

The third section should outline: (i) the identity of the person responsible for identifying the corrective action, (ii) the associated beneficiary, (iii) the date when the corrective action was identified, and (iv) the activities affected by the non-conformity, including the title, reference, task, and WP identification. Additionally, this section will include (v) a comprehensive description of the proposed corrective action.

Finally, the fourth section will detail the decision regarding the proposed corrective action, including: (i) the individual responsible for making the decision, (ii) the decision's approval status, and (iii) the date when the decision was made.

6 Scientific/Technical/User Objectives (SO/TO/UO) and Performance Indicators (KPI)

iDriving outlines 4 Scientific Objectives (SO), 1 Technical Objective (TO), and 2 User Objectives (UO), all of which are aligned with the project’s work program. The key outcomes will be measured using KPIs and validated through the activities of the respective work packages. For each Scientific, Technical, or User Objective, a table has been created, listing the key expected outcomes of the SO/TO alongside the corresponding performance indicators. In addition to the indicators listed below, the success of each activity will be assessed based on the number of publications produced in relevant fields, including contributions to scientific conferences or journals.

6.1 SO.1 - KPIs 1-3

SO.1 deals with "Innovative Communication Protocols" (WP3). Its expected results shown below and their respective KPIs shown below are related to these specific Scientific Activities: SA 1.1: Common connectivity catalogue for different types of vehicles and automation levels (KR1); (ii) SA 1.2: Semantic Interoperability Validation Service (KR2); SA 1.3: Usage Control Policy Analysis Algorithm (KR3).

Table 4 - SO.1 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR1: Common connectivity catalogue for different types of vehicles and automation levels	KPI1.1: New type of users on the catalogue > 5; KPI1.2: Safety-related Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) mapped to ISAD concept > 5 KPI1.3: Incorporate different types of vehicles with different automation levels
KR2: Semantic Interoperability Validation Service	KPI2.1: Interoperable devices > 2 KPI2.2: Sovereign devices > 2
KR3: Usage Control Policy Analysis Algorithm	KPI3.1: Usage control policies > 5

6.2 SO.2 - KPIs 4-7

SO.2 deals with "Efficient and accurate monitoring services" (WP3&4). Its expected results are shown below and their respective KPIs are related to these specific Scientific Activities: SA 2.1: Visual object detection and identification (KR4); SA 2.2: AI-Powered analysis of object’s behaviour (KR5); SA 2.3: Analysis of environmental conditions (KR6); SA 2.4: High-level autonomous control of UAVs (KR7).

Table 5 - SO.2 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR4: Accurate and efficient detection of objects of interest on-site	KPI4.1: Object classes >10; KPI4.2: Detection accuracy >80% (mAP); KPI4.3: Processing time ≥10fps (edge), >25fps (non-edge) KPI4.4: Reduced latency for results to iDriving compared to a non-edge solution > 20%
KR5: Efficient abnormal driving patterns and traffic violation detection	KPI5.1: Number of classes >5 KPI5.2: Detection of abnormal driving patterns >80% (mAP) KPI5.3: Traffic violation detection > 85% KPI5.4: Near-real time detections >25fps
KR6: Accurate monitoring of urban and secondary roads' microclimates and real-time environmental analysis	KPI6.1: Environmental monitoring accuracy >85% based also on historical data KPI6.2: Notifications < 10 secs
KR7: Off-line and online path planning solutions for regions' mapping and incidents tracking	KPI7.1: 20% reduced scanning operations' time for data collection out of regions of interest KPI7.2: 30% increased awareness in the incidents' sites, compared to the deployment of human personnel

6.3 SO.3 - KPIs 8-11

SO.3 deals with "Digital Twins for Enhanced Event Analysis and Early Warning Mechanisms" (WP5). Its expected results are shown below and their respective KPIs are connected with the following Scientific Activities (SA): SA 3.1: AI-based updates of Safety Criteria Catalogue (SCC) [KR8]; SA 3.2: Digital Twin for simulation of road conditions and prediction of dangerous events [KR9]; SA 3.3: Incident identification and warning mechanisms [KR10]; SA 3.4: Optimal traffic management for congestion avoidance and improved safety environment [KR11].

Table 6 - SO.3 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR8: Prediction Model Library for SCC and validation of Influential Safety Variables	KPI8.1: 20% improvement in predictive accuracy of safety KPIs compared to current models KPI8.2: Identify and validate at least 10 new influential variables that impact safety metrics KPI8.3: 15% reduction in FP and FN
KR9: Digital Twin's Simulation of Road Conditions and Prediction of dangerous events;	KPI9.1: Achieve a 90% accuracy level in traffic condition simulations compared to real-world data

	KPI9.2: Reduce the data-to-dashboard reporting latency by 15% KPI9.3: Achieve a predictive accuracy of at least 85%
KR10: Real-time Identification of Incidents and warning mechanisms	KPI10.1: Achieve a 95% accuracy rate in the identification of atypical situations KPI10.2: Reduce the time between incident identification and response initiation by at least 10%. KPI10.3: Produce warning messages covering all the scenarios and road users
KR11: Traffic Flow Improvement for safer roads	KPI11.1: A minimum of a 10% decrease in travel times as compared to existing solutions KPI11.2: Reduction in traffic-related accidents by at least 10%

6.4 SO4 - KPIs 12-13

SO.4 deals with " Intelligence for improved maintenance operations" (WP3-5). Its expected results are shown below and their respective KPIs relate to the following Scientific Activities (SA): SA 4.1: 3D representation for enhanced visualization (KR11); SA 4.2: Defect detection of road infrastructure at the local level (KR13); SA 4.3: Digital Twin for cost-effective maintenance strategies (KR14).

Table 7 - SO.4 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR12: Enhanced 3D Rendering and integration with AI techniques for comprehensive road analysis	KPI12.1: Achieve a minimum 5x boost in rendering performance compared to traditional methods. KPI12.2: Reduce model memory footprint by at least 30% compared to traditional implementations.
KR13: Real-time and accurate defect detection model	KPI13.1: Detection accuracy > 90% (mAP) KPI13.2: Real-time processing speed ≥25fps
KR14: Risk-based DT for Maintenance Optimization	KPI14.1: Achieve > 90% accuracy rate in the AI-driven risk modelling for identifying potential road maintenance issues. KPI14.2: 15% reduction in maintenance costs compared to traditional methods. KPI14.3: 20% reduction of maintenance decision-making time. KPI14.4: 10% reduction in incidents related to road maintenance issues

6.5 TO.1 & KPIs 15-18

TO.1 deals with "Integration and Visualization of Mobile, In-Vehicle, and UAV Data Services for Enhanced Driving Experiences" (WP3-5). Its expected results are shown below and their respective KPIs relate to the following Technical Activities (TA): TA 1.1: Mobile and in-vehicle apps (KR15); TA 2.2: Data acquisition from UAVs (KR16); TA 1.3: C2 with enhanced visualization features (KR17); TA 1.4 Integration of services (KR18).

Table 8 - TO.1 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR15: Mobile and in-vehicle app for early user warnings	KPI15.1: Number of active users of the application in a specific time period >80% of users on the road KPI15.2: Frequency and duration of application usage per user >90% of driving time KPI15.3: Percentage of users who enable and utilize early warning features >90%
KR16: UAV with onboard processing capabilities	KPI16.1: Percentage of coverage of monitored areas >90%
KR17: C2XR command and control center	KPI17.1: Real-time Data Accuracy >99% KPI17.2: 20% improvement of the emergency Communication Effectiveness KPI17.3: 30% increase in the satisfaction of control center operators
KR18: iDriving Unified Road Safety Ecosystem	KPI18.1: Three versions of the Ecosystem (M18, M26, M34)

6.6 UO.1 & KPIs

UO.1 deals with "SCC Production, Requirements and validation" (WP2). Its expected results shown below and their respective KPIs are connected with the following User Activities (UA): UA 1.1: Safety Criteria Catalogue formulation (KR19); UA 1.2: User & safety requirements (KR20); UA 1.3: Use case design & stakeholder engagement (KR21); UA 1.4 Ethics & legal framework (KR22).

Table 9 - UO.1 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR19: SCC Catalogue with KPIs	KPI19.1: Implementation of SCC in 6 trials KPI19.2: Harmonized SCC with safety KPIs accepted in 10 EU countries KPI19.3: Published 1 journal paper and 2 conference papers on SCC implementation and validation
KR20: Open standards traffic safety network	KPI20.1: User-defined requirements that are clear and broad enough

	to ensure that all stakeholders' needs are met
KR21: All technological KRs implemented in PUCs	KPI21.1: KRs integrated into all Pilot Use Cases KPI21.2: 6 workshops with stakeholders (per PUC, per scenario)
KR22: Respect ethical and legal aspects of EU	KP22.1: Number of recommendations, convergence of iDriving with relevant legislation and ethical demands

6.7 UO.2 & KPIs

UO.2 deals with "Pilot implementation and evaluation" (WP6). Its expected results are shown below and their respective KPIs relate to the following User Activities (UA): UA 2.1: Development of the validation scenario and evaluation methodology (KR23); UA 2.2: Field trials, testing, and training (KR24).

Table 10 - UO.2 Indicators

Key Results	Key Performance Indicators
KR23: Development of methodology for all 6 trials and evaluation and validation results	KPI23.1: Accurately define evaluation methodology and execute validation of the results
KR24: Successful deployment of field trials	KPI24.1: Details on trial organization and implementation; KPI24.2: All users must be familiar with the platform

7 Summary

This report represents the first deliverable of WPI and the overall project, outlining the management processes established to oversee iDriving and maintain quality standards throughout its duration. In terms of project management, it details the internal organization of the consortium, explaining the collective bodies and individual roles, as well as the responsibilities assigned to each. Additionally, it describes the tools used for document creation and sharing, ensuring smooth communication within the consortium and with the Commission. The report also includes guidelines for document creation, deliverable submission, and meeting coordination.

Moreover, the report introduces a comprehensive Quality Assurance Plan (QAP), which will be applied throughout the iDriving project's lifecycle. The QAP addresses the organizational structure from a quality management perspective, defining the hierarchy and the distribution of quality assurance responsibilities within the consortium. It outlines the processes and tools designed to facilitate effective communication between consortium members and the European Commission through the Project Coordinator. The plan also specifies procedures for producing and submitting high-quality reports and deliverables in a timely manner. In addition, the QAP details the strategy for maintaining the quality of research and implementing corrective measures to address any issues or non-conformities that may arise. Lastly, the QAP provides a set of indicators to monitor progress across the project's activities.

A. APPENDIX

A.1 Logos

In line with Article 17.2 “Visibility — European flag and funding statement” Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, all communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the project will acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Figure 2 - EU Flag & Funding Statement

iDriving is a project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon Europe Programme (HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01) under Grant Agreement No. 101147004.

Quality of information – Disclaimer

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information.

Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them”.

iDriving Logo

The file containing the official iDriving logo, as shown in the figure below, will be available in the shared repository for download and use by Consortium partners throughout the project.

Figure 3 - Project Logo

A.2 Presentation and Document Templates

As mentioned earlier, to ensure uniformity across all project-related presentations—whether for internal or public audiences—ACCELIGENCE as the Leader of Dissemination Work Package (WP7) has provided a set of templates. These include presentation formats, deliverable templates, and internal review forms for deliverables. All templates are available in the shared repository. Below are a few examples:

A.2.1 Presentation Template

Figure 4 - Project Presentation Template

A2.2. Deliverable Template Front Page

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

DX.X – Title of the document report

Author(s):	Names of authors
Leading Partner:	Name of the organisation
Version - Status:	V1 – Final

Submission Date:	29/02/2024
Dissemination Level:	PUBLIC

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message: ©iDriving Consortium, 2024-2027. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Report information

Purpose of the Report	Three lines executive summary/purpose of the current deliverable report		
Relevant Work package:	WP7		
Relevant Task:			
Contributors:	XXX.XXX.XXX		
Next version Title:	XX/XX/202X	Next version Date:	XX/XX/202X
Official Submission Date:	XX/XX/202X	Actual Submission Date:	XX/XX/202X

Figure 5 - Deliverable reports 1st page

A.2.3 Deliverable Internal review form

The form is divided into several sections:

- 1 Process used for Deliverables review:** Includes a disclaimer, review process description, reviewer information, and a 'Overall Review Result' table with options like 'Fully accepted', 'Accepted with reservation', 'Rejected unless modified/suggested', and 'Fully rejected'.
- 2 Suggested actions to the authors:** A list of four numbered items for the reviewer to specify: 2.1 following changes, 2.2 missing chapters, 2.3 required changes, and 2.4 further improvements.
- 3 Comments of Reviewer:** A section for detailed feedback with sub-topics:
 - Topic A: General comments:** Focuses on overall thoroughness and project objective alignment.
 - Topic B: Relevance:** Asks if the deliverable is relevant to the project's goals.
 - Topic C: Methodological framework soundness:** Checks if the methodology is sound and clearly explained.
 - Topic D: Quality of achievements:** Evaluates the evidence and quality of the results.
- Footer:** Contains the iDRIVING logo, project title, start/end dates, duration, total cost, coordinator information, and a grid of consortium member logos.

Figure 6 - Deliverables' internal review form

A.2.4 Minutes Template

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated
with Next-Gen Technologies

iDriving Meeting Minutes

Meeting Type, Date, Place

Author(s):	Names of authors
Version - Status:	V1.0
Meeting Date:	17/09/2024
Minutes Date:	17/09/2024
Classification:	Confidential

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.

Copyright message: ©iDriving Consortium, 2024-2027. This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorized provided the source is acknowledged.

Document History

Version	Date	Author	Partner	Description
0.1				First version
0.2				
0.3				
1.0				Final version sent to partners

Participants List

Organisation	First/Last name	Attending
CERTH		

Figure 7 - Minutes Template

iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH)

iDriving Consortium

The Project "iDriving - Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies" has received funding from the European Union's Horizon EUROPE Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101147004.